

Higher order physics for neuroscience.

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Often in physics, we come across problems demanding insight into observations for numerical comprehension. We decide to focus on computational neuroscience for source quantization with the help of machine learning. In particular we are focused on the PTSD problem with respect to optimization to discern from source signal and noise. The TBI spike is evident as a singularity conforming to a discontinuity in pathology and connectivity for neural recordings. We then localize for ground truth and validate against known methods in 2 photon microscopy. (Stefanovic et al). To supplement that, we measure and observe neural response with MEG recordings. Alternatively we adopt the quantum Ising Annealing algorithm and Grover's search for EEG source analysis. Some preliminary filters such as notch filtering and ICA are implemented for noise removal. We observe extraordinary global convergence and accurate and fast optimization based on quantum computing. We perform our simulation on the DWAVE 2000 computer and collect our EEG data using the Muse headband.

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